

2021 University Research Symposium

Welcome from Vice Chancellor for Research and Opening Keynote Presentation

Welcome

- [Mladen Vouk](#), Vice Chancellor for Research and Innovation
 - [View Video](#)

Opening Keynote Presenters

- [Jean Goodwin](#), SAS Institute, Department of Communication
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 - [Kathie Dello](#), NC State Climate Office
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Event Description:

Vice Chancellor Mladen Vouk and keynote presenters Dr. Jean Goodwin, SAS Institute Distinguished Professor of Rhetoric and Technical Communication, and Dr. Kathie Dello, state climatologist and director of the North Carolina State Climate Office, kicked things off March 22. Goodwin gave an overview of the public's present perception of climate change and outlines some best practices for effectively communicating about climate change. Dello summarized some of the specific challenges North Carolina is currently facing as a result of climate change — and how NC State can continue to help address these challenges.

You can [watch](#) the discussion in its entirety on the NC State Research YouTube channel.

Online Resources Shared:

- Public Science Listserv: <https://publicscience.ncsu.edu/google-groups-sign-up/>
- NC State Climate Office: <https://climate.ncsu.edu/>
- North Carolina Institute for Climate Studies (NCICS): <https://ncics.org/>

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- NC Sea Grant: <https://ncseagrant.ncsu.edu/>
 - Southeast Climate Adaptation Science Center: <https://secasc.ncsu.edu/>
 - NC Clean Energy Technology Center <https://nccleantech.ncsu.edu/>
 - Database of State Incentives for Renewables & Efficiency:
<https://www.dsireusa.org/>
 - Inaugural Cohort of Impact Scholars announcement:
<https://research.ncsu.edu/2021/02/18/inaugural-cohort-of-impact-scholars-announced/>
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